

TRADITIONAL DRUGS:

Small molecules easy to obtain through
CHEMICAL SYNTHESIS

or from **MEDICINAL PLANTS**

VS

BIOPHARMACEUTICALS:

Macro-molecules (**PROTEINS**) difficult to synthesise chemically (es. **HORMONES, ANTIBODIES, ANTIGENS** for **SUBUNIT VACCINES** formulation and **DIAGNOSTIC ASSAYS**)

PAST (in the '70s)
Extraction and purification from
animal/human organs

PRESENT (since '80s)
Biotechnologies

PLANTS are considered as a valid alternative to traditional cellular “biofactories” to produce heterologous proteins for biopharmaceutical purposes. The DNA sequence can be inserted into the plant genome and transmitted to the progeny (stable expression). An alternative method can be adopted in which the DNA is not transmitted to the progeny and the protein is only temporarily produced in plant tissues (transient expression).

The **PLANT BIOFACTORY**-based transient expression approach used in REPRODIVAC has the potential to result in: i) ease and rapidity of production scale up at low cost; ii) simplification of the purification procedures; iii) improvement of vaccine efficacy; iv) development of ready-to-use diagnostic tools able to differentiate infected from vaccinated animals (DIVA) in surveillance programs and international trade of livestock.